

Modelling of the auto-ignition of hotspots in hydrogen air mixtures

R.Ezekwesili*¹, M.Bellenoue², C.Strozzi³, M.Bohon⁴

¹R.Ezekwesili, Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Fluid Dynamics, r.ezekwesili@tu-berlin.de

²M. Bellenoue, PPRIME, ISAE-ENSMA, CNRS, Université de Poitiers, marc.bellenoue@ensma.fr

³C. Strozzi, PPRIME, Université de Poitiers, ISAE-ENSMA, CNRS, camille.strozzi@ensma.fr

⁴M.Bohon, Technische Universität Berlin, Institute of Fluid Dynamics, m.bohon@tu-berlin.de

Abstract: In the context of pressure gain combustion, areas of increased reactivity called hotspots may arise in a chamber of premixed fuel and oxidizer. Auto-ignition of these hotspots leads to different combustion propagation modes including detonations. Detonations should be suppressed in constant volume combustors (CVC) and shockless explosion combustors (SEC) but promoted in detonation engines. Controlling the transitions between hotspot regimes is one of the keys to developing pressure gain combustion and wider combustion applications. Hydrogen is an attractive fuel for the future of aviation and therefore it is important that its combustion characteristics are understood and mastered. This paper aims to model the auto-ignition of hydrogen hotspots and the resulting combustion modes using the INSFLA code provided by the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology. The INSFLA code simulates 1-dimensional reacting flows for multi-step chemistry and multi-species transport models, uses full compressible Navier-Stokes equations and performs spatial discretization using the finite difference method. The code will be adapted to model hotspots in the context of autoignition. The model adopted for the hotspot is one where a linear temperature gradient is assumed within the hotspot radius and an auto-ignition wave propagates due to autoignition along this temperature gradient as shown in figure 1. Integral in building this mathematical model is selecting the appropriate reaction mechanism, running 0-dimensional simulations to determine the autoignition wave speed and heat release characteristics. Moreover, planar and spherical configurations will be tested to observe the effects geometry has on detonation development behavior. Experimental work exploring the effects of hydrogen on autoignition behavior will be completed using the experimental set-up shown in figure 2. The results from the numerical model will be compared to the experimental results to assess to what extent the model represents the structure of hotspots, the mechanism of the autoignition wave propagation, the interaction of the autoignition wave with the acoustic wave and the effects that hydrogen has on the detonation development behavior.

Figure 1: Temporal evolution of temperature and pressure during an autoignition wave propagating through a hotspot and transitioning to a detonation.

Figure 2: Experimental setup used within this project

Keywords: Hotspot, autoignition, detonation, transition

Acknowledgment: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 956803